

THE IMPORTANCE OF EXTRUDED FEEDS IN PROTEIN METABOLISM IN FISH

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Abstract : *This in intensive fisheries in the article being grown fishes between proteins exchange in disorders fish of food importance about in detail data given being in this extruded feed granular from feed difference and secrets given . Extruder feeds basin in the water not sinking as a result fishes by complete acceptance to be done and the water contamination and excess food persistence prevention takes*

Key words : *fish, protein, granule, extruder, omukhta feed, intensive, ETS, amino acid.*

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Most of the fish grown in the intensive fisheries of our republic are more prone to metabolic disorders and disorders, and in most cases, these diseases are not paid attention to. This is a group of diseases, which are characterized by various physiological conditions and pathologo-anatomical changes, and are caused by the lack of protein substances important for the body. It occurs due to the insufficient amount of various amino acids coming to the body through food or the insufficient amount of synthesis in the body, the reason for this is the lack of natural nutrients rich in protein in the rations of fish.

Effective methods of diagnosis and prevention of these diseases have not been developed. This, in turn, is likely to reduce the economic potential of fisheries. In order to prevent this, taking into account the climate and local conditions of our Republic, as well as the ecological situation, it is carried out by adding nutrients rich in natural vitamins, organic, inorganic and mineral substances to the diet of fish. Due to the limitation of such opportunities in the intensification of the fishing industry, various vitamins, protein-rich organic, inorganic and mineral supplements, premixes, drugs, fish oil, blue mass, animal liver, greens, etc. are added to their feed. . When

artificially feeding fish, their ration composition, nutritional value and biologically active substances should be balanced in order to prevent protein metabolism disorders.

the topic . The protein requirement of fish is much higher than that of other farmed animals, and the total protein requirement depends on the type and age of the fish. For example: proteins should make up 31-38% of feed for carp, 35-40% for trout, 38-40% for crucian carp, 40-42% for African flounder and local river flounder, and up to 50% is required for young fish.

Mainly in young fish, when the metabolism of proteins is disturbed, it is possible to see a decrease in appetite at first. When the disease is chronic, clinical symptoms begin to appear for a long time (after 1.5 months or more). Fish lag far behind in growth and development, dysproteinemia can be observed in the fish organism. Disruption of protein metabolism in African flounder causes various abnormalities in the stomach (thickening of the stomach wall, ulcers, and necrosis) and causes the fish to stop growing. An excess of non-exchangeable amino acids in the body or a violation of their ratio leads to fatty dystrophy of the liver .

Diseases of protein metabolism disorders in fish mainly occur when fish are fed with foods that do not meet their nutritional needs or when they are given more than the norm, in hypovitaminosis, when calcium and phosphorus metabolism is disturbed, as a result of various parasitic diseases. The disease is observed in fish of different breeds and ages, and mainly young fish are more susceptible.

fish organism or a violation of their ratio leads to fatty dystrophy of the liver .

The disease occurs during the warm season, when their diet consists of high protein foods, including fish and meat. The disease sometimes occurs when fish that have been spoiled or stored for a long time eat meat and bones, and when they eat fatty foods that are low in vitamins. Infections, toxicosis, metabolic disorders and close keeping of fish play an important role in the origin of the disease .

Excess histidine causes various abnormalities in the stomach (thickening of the stomach wall, ulcers and necrosis) and causes fish to stop growing.

When carp are fed a low-protein diet, energy deficiency syndrome (ETS) occurs in fish due to rapid depletion of energy sources. In this, the fish rotates around the core, turns to the side, looks up, swims for a while and then turns again. Decreased growth and changes in physiological parameters (body moisture, crude protein, whey protein, sodium and calcium ions). It causes fatty dystrophy of the liver in many species of fish, especially (salmon and sea bass). In addition, it leads to a decrease in reproduction, accumulation of fat in the visceral cavity and tissues, and an increase in the amount of fat in the muscles (in sea bass and other types of fish).

Protein fish tissues main structural is a part of and therefore normal growth for for important food is considered

Fish organism known functions perform for important has been enzymes , hormones and intestine epithelial cells such as to protein based on products work release and outdated tissues again recovery for to protein needs is considered

In our country artificial fishing in the basins growing the fish feeding basically addition ration based on take is going

Fish in feeding granular nutrients wide applied is getting married this nutrients in the water sinking because of carp fish enough level eat can't and from this except sunken food basin water pollution take come , this processes due to in fish food acceptance to do getting worse proteins exchange process to the violation take will come .

Research methodology. Studies It was conducted at the "Outsider Fish" fishery belonging to the Lower Chirchik district.

For research, two groups of experimental and control groups were formed, each consisting of 500 heads of three-month-old carp fry.

Extruded feed was given to the control group, and extruded feed was given to the fish in the experimental group. The experiments lasted 90 days.

prepared extruded and granulated feed mixture is as follows (100 kg contains 20% corn meal, 10% wheat bran, 28% wheat meal, 12% barley meal and 25% mash, 2% alfalfa flour).

Experience during the fish grow and development analysis done went

Experience At the end of control in the group the fish average the body weight 0.4 kg organize reached if experience in the group the fish average weight 0.8 kg organize did

Figure 1: Example as hunted carp fish

Extruded food giving went experience in the group in fish grow and development control to the gurhi relative to 0.4 kg high to be with an extruder food in the water that it did not sink for fishes by complete acceptance that he did and necessary with protein substances food through received with explained .

Summary : In fish occurring proteins exchange violation diseases prevention in getting feed how to structure have the fact that very important occupation is enough

Intensive fishing in farms extruded soft from feeds use feed not sinking because of fishes by complete acceptance to be done through to my body enough amount protein of substances fall observed and from this except excess extravagance and the water pollution prevention received will be

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